

IMPORTANCE OF USING MULTIMEDIA TOOLS AND TEACHING MATERIALS AS EDUCATIONAL STANDARTS

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Abstract: This article highlights several ways to learn English successfully and some of the modern learning multimedia tools and usage of effective teaching materials to language learners well.

Keywords: English, multimedia tolls, information technologies, independent language learning, educational teaching materials.

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan, the national educational process is forming the experience of using multimedia tools, since it is also an urgent necessity. Developing information tools are factors like people's ability, initiative, creative approach to work, intellectual activity, and autonomous growth of their knowledge and abilities, in addition to the traditional opportunities that determine the base of social progress in modern society. The process of generating information pertaining to the creation, transmission, and receiving of massive volumes of information anticipates the advancement of computer technology in a variety of human endeavors. Human thinking has advanced to the point where technicalization and computerization are opportunistically advancing into not only the many domains of production but also the fields of culture.

Method and methodology

Nowadays, English language is playing an essential role in our lives as it helps in communication. It is the main language for studying any subject all over the world. Therefore, the graduates of any Uzbek educational institution up to the university level must be proficient in at least two foreign languages, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev announced in May in 2021. In order to ensure the implementation of the above-mentioned decision, teachers in schools are trying to organize classes well. Organizing multimedia lessons and further increasing students' interest in English is becoming the main goal and task of all teachers today.

We all know that schoolchildren are young and their brains are at an evolving stage. Not only schoolchildren, but also all learners can learn only a certain part of the subject i.e. 25% when they first hear new information. Learners can remember one-third of the new information. If they both see and hear, they remember 50% of the information. In the case of data using interactive multimedia technologies, this figure is 75%. It is clear from this that the use of multimedia in the classroom is much more useful and important for students as well. By using multimedia tools in the educational

process, teachers are able to perform tasks that are of great pedagogical and psychological importance. The information provided using multimedia tools is more deeply assimilated and more understandable and clear to readers. And through this, the reader can also save his time. and the information obtained by such a method is stored in the memory of the reader for a long time. The participation of primary school students as passive listeners will be reduced by this way and also multimedia programs will be introduced to improve inquiry and cognitive activity, and art will be introduced into the educational process. In other words, multimedia activates the motivations of education, such as emotional and aesthetic impact, purposefulness, research.

The term "multimedia" refers to a complicated idea and modern information technology. Multimedia uses a variety of information sources to gather data, including text, tables, graphics, speech, animation, and music and video. conducts labor, storage, processing, and transmission activities. A new, upgraded level of interactive (dialogic) communication called a multimedia "human computer" allows the user to access a wide variety of detailed information. Use of multimedia tools for entertainment and education It is employed in industries like advertising and marketing. One of the current concerns is how to educate pupils in elementary school using multimedia tools. Both pedagogically and psychologically, the employment of multimedia tools in the educational process is crucial. The information provided in it is more thoroughly understood, time can be saved, the information received is retained in memory for a long time, the participation of students in junior high school as passive learners is reduced, multimedia programs aimed at enhancing curiosity and cognitive activity are implemented, and education art is incorporated into the process. In other words, motives like emotional-aesthetic impact, pursuing an objective, and inquiry are activated by multimedia education. It is well known that a student only retains a third of what he or she views and just a quarter of what they hear.

RESEARCH OUTCOME

The method of organizing the teaching process based on multimedia tools is fundamentally different from the traditional teaching method, and it is for teachers and students of primary school:

- Presentation of educational material in the form of images;
- Teaching is differentiated and individualized;
- Evaluating the learning and learning process, communicating with the other;
- Self-control and correction in the process of mastering the educational material;
- Demonstrate the studied topics and observe their interrelation;

The work carried out in this regard is related to the improvement and introduction of multimedia capabilities of modern information technologies in the educational system, their purposeful use leads to an increase in the effectiveness of the educational

process. By incorporating these concepts into every subject covered in elementary school, the multimedia tool broadens the span of understanding of these concepts. Meyer's guidelines for effective multimedia. The systematization of educational content through the use of multimedia tools during instruction helps students freely select and switch between comprehensive and incomplete educational possibilities. The modern form of instructional instruments includes information transfer in addition to communication.

Modern, multi-disciplinary, subject-focused multimedia educational tools must be developed and used in the process of implementing individualized education with the aid of technology. Extensive databases, educational knowledge bases, expert learning systems, artificial intelligence systems, and laboratory techniques with the capacity to develop mathematical models of the investigated process and phenomena are among them. Multimedia tools in education provides an opportunity to ensure the humanization of education, increase the efficiency of the educational process and development of the learner's personal qualities, communicative and social skills.

DISCUSSION

According to the possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as according to the qualities of compatibility, interactivity, flexibility of various types of multimedia educational information, multimedia is useful and productive education. Comparing digital multimedia to other information presentation methods, providing interactivity is one of its key achievements. Interactive learning refers to giving the recipient the appropriate information based on their needs. You can have some degree of control over how information is presented thanks to interactivity. For example, students can modify the program's settings individually, examine the results, respond to inquiries about their specific preferences, and choose how quickly and how many times to repeat certain lessons. However, it is possible to use multimedia, it's crucial to keep a few things in mind. Multimedia educational content should be simple to understand and provided using current data and practical techniques.

Similar to using textbooks, the educational method of using multimedia technologies can only be supplemented with content when the teacher is actively involved in not just imparting knowledge but also in supporting, assisting, and leading the students. Presentations enhanced with stunning visuals or animations typically stand out more than simple text and can add the required emotional depth to the information being delivered. People with diverse mental and age features of learning and receiving knowledge might employ multimedia technologies in conjunction with distinct educational orientations (styles). Some learners prefer direct reading. some people prefer to study and get knowledge via hearing, while others prefer to watch (videos).

The main problems and disadvantages of using multimedia tools in education. There are also some common disadvantages of using multimedia in education. They include the division of attention, complications in creating materials, more time requirements, problems in setting up and using software and hardware, difficulties in the process of reading information from a computer screen, and other aspects.

CONCLUSION

Everyone needs to use multimedia at all times for business now. Modern information and communication technology' use of multimedia tools has ingrained them into our daily lives. The quality of education and learner efficiency are both improved by the employment of multimedia technology in the educational process. The use of multimedia technologies to visualize and model macro and microcosmic processes, as well as to capture priceless moments and generate entertainment materials, paves the way for enjoyment.

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